

VUNOKLANG MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION

(Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola)

ISSN: 2276-8114

Website: www.vmjste.net

REFORMING AUTOMOBILE TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION CURRICULUM FOR GLOBAL WARMING

Oguche, I. O.¹ and Okuta, S.²

¹Department of Technology, Airforce Institute of Technology, Kaduna.

²Department of Automobile Technology, Federal College of Education (Technical), Gombe.

Corresponding Author: innojoguche@gmail.com

Abstract

Emissions from motor vehicle exhaust contribute much in the pollution of our environment and this has a significant impact on the global warming or climate change. Therefore, this paper looked into the influence of such emissions in the environment and general health of the public. Solutions to this development will only be achieved through the reformation of automobile technology education curriculum which will enable scholars and general public to understand; the impact of automobile emissions in climate change, need for inclusion of catalytic converter in motor vehicle and possible ways of reducing emissions from motor vehicle. Conclusion was drawn based on the issues discussed.

Keywords: Automobile, Technology Education, Curriculum Reform, Climate Change

Introduction

In Nigeria, there are a lot of jobless youths, who have been churned out of technical colleges and other craft schools. According to (Okuta & Enoch, 2018) these youths could have been gainfully employed or self-employed, or further their education. However, it has become clear by experience that most of the motor vehicle mechanic works (MVMW) craftsmen/women who have graduated from technical colleges are neither employable nor possess the entry qualification for higher education. Following the population growth and migration as a result of insurgency has also raised the number of motor vehicles in the country drastically. However, the number of craftsmen available to maintain and repair these automobiles is inadequate, yet youths suffer unemployment in the midst of job opportunities. This fact therefore, challenges the technology institutions in the training of MVMW craftsmen who shall keep automobiles in safe and efficient operating conditions. There is no much distinct between technical education and technology education. Technical education is the acquisition of skills and techniques in a chosen occupation or professional to enable an individual earn a living. Sanusi (2003) defined technical education as a training for an individual to help him acquire skills, knowledge and attitude in a particular occupational area for employment with respect to societal needs. In the same vein, technology education is a type of education that provides a wider range of skill levels from basic entry level skill to highly technical skills requiring a high degree of specialization and competence, (Elom, 2012). The primary purpose of both type of education is to impart to

recipients, skills, scientific knowledge and competence that can enable them work very effectively in industrial and commercial ventures through a systematic and well-prepared programme training and instruction. Technology education has many programmes as a course of study. Some of these areas of study include; building technology education, electrical/electronics technology education, automobile technology, metal work, woodwork, Air condition and refrigeration among others.

Automobile technology is one of the major study areas in technology education. Automobile technology education is therefore, the study of motor vehicle or automechanics. As a course of study, it can be offered in technical colleges, colleges of education (technical) polytechnics and universities. Automobile is a self-moving object. Azubuoke (2018) described automobile as a passenger vehicle designed for operation on ordinary roads and typically having four or more wheels. It may be either a gasoline or diesel internal combustion engine and more recently electrical. Also Uneke (2015) stated that automobile technology refers to a vehicle consisting of four wheels or more and powered by an internal combustion engine. Automobiles are used to transport people and items from one location to another location. After years of various designs, inventors were able to develop a functional general decisions that is utilized by major Automakers as the foundation of their designs. Automobiles generally use gasoline to fuel the internal engine, but technological advances have led to the design of vehicles that can run using electricity, solar energy and water. Automobiles have different systems but they work together for them to be functional. These systems are classified according to their functions in automobile technology curriculum for the effective study of the contents. Curriculum is the plan for action or a written document, which include strategies for achieving desired educational goals or ends. (Ijiga, 2010) said it all involves all programmes of activities designed by the school to enable learners attain, as far as possible desirable educational goals or ends. Automobile technology curriculum should be reformed from time to time because of the tremendous changes in technology which influence conditions in our environments.

Curriculum reform is the modification of an existing curriculum with the hope of providing a better curricular programme (Fafunwa 1997). It is the introduction of novelties in terms of content and practice, the alteration of what is established, a novel content, practice and method. One of the unstable factors that may cause for curriculum reform is the global warming. Global warming, or global warming and environmental pollution/degradation are new realities staring the human community in the face today. With their deleterious effects. The effects of global warming are very disturbing in our day to day activities. Global warming is a significant and lasting change in the statistical distribution of weather patterns over periods ranging from decades to millions of years. It may be a change in average weather conditions (Ijiga and Ujah 2015). Global warming is caused by factors that include; oceanic processes, biotic processes, variation in solar radiation received by earth, human induced alteration of the natural world such as the emissions from motor vehicles.

Motor vehicle emissions are one of the leading cause of air pollution (Van & Dutty, 2000). In the same vein, Sharma and Eneh (2011) stated that, in case of noise pollution, the dominant source is the motor vehicle, producing about 99% of all unwanted noise worldwide. In Nigeria something must be done in order to cope with the global warming because some common types of pollution have main effects on humans. Adverse air quickly can kill organisms, including humans and ozone pollution can cause respiratory disease such as cardiovascular disease, throat inflammation, chest pain and congestion, (Lorenz, 2007; Kallman, 2008; Eneh, 2011). Therefore, curriculum of

automobile technology should be reformed to create awareness among teachers, scholars and uses of motor vehicle on some of the dangerous outcome of motor vehicle driving and highlight some of the remedies to emissions from the motor vehicle. Thus, knowing the impact of automobile in climate change, understanding the need for catalytic converter in motor vehicle, and ways of reducing emissions from motor vehicle.

Impact of Automobile Emission on Global Warming

For years now, many scientists and other scholars have been raising concerns about global warming and the consequences of the warming of earth. And excessive amount of carbon in the atmosphere contributes to global warming, with emissions from factories and power plant being a major contributor to increased levels of atmospheric carbon. However automobile emissions are another major source of carbon. Emissions from automobile increase pollution levels, which lead to all manner of health problems. Understanding automobile carbon emission and what car owners can do to reduce it will go a long way toward addressing the effects of carbon emissions (Kerstetter 2004). Carbon traps heat in the atmosphere, preventing it from escaping from the earth. Some scientists theorize that this has led to a warmer earth over the past century, increasing the odds of severe weather patterns, droughts and other problems. Consequently, governments around the world have it a goal to reduce their carbon emissions. Reducing emission from vehicle is key to this effort. Carbon emissions include a number of different chemicals and particulates that are produced when fuel is burned in an engine. Some of the major substances found in a vehicles exhaust include carbon (iv) oxide, ozone and carbon monoxide. Other chemicals often found in exhaust gasses are, Benzene and nitrogen oxides. Many of these chemicals serve an important purposes in different parts of atmosphere, but they can have had bad consequences when human beings inhale them directly. Therefore, Global warming endangers our health, jeopardize our national security, and threatens other basic human needs. Some of the impacts include high temperatures, rising seas, and severe flooding and droughts and they are increasing commonly. Our personal vehicles are a major cause of global warming. Collectively, cars, and trucks account for nearly one-fifth of all emissions, emitting around 24 pounds of carbon (iv) oxide and other global warming gases for every gallon of gas. About five pounds comes from the extraction, production, and delivery of the fuel, while the great bulk of heat trapping emissions comes from vehicle tail pipe. Vehicle emission have a number of harmful effects on human health. Although people with healthy livings are affected by these chemicals, individuals with living problems are at a particularly high risk of being harmed by vehicle emissions. Those who suffer from conditions such as asthma chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases (COPD) experience worsening symptoms when they are exposed to excessive amounts of vehicle exhaust.

Many of the chemicals found in vehicle emission have been identified as carcinogens. Some experts have suggested that about half of cancers related to outdoor air pollution can be tied to vehicle emission. Reduce emission and there will be fewer cancer causing chemicals in the air that people breathe every day. Furthermore, irritants in vehicle exhaust can cause the obstruction of airways and other breathing problems and contribute to other health issues. (Sharma & Eneh, (2011). The elderly and young children are also at a higher risk of having an adverse reaction to vehicle exhaust than other members of the population.

Need for catalytic converter in the motor vehicles

A catalytic converter is an exhaust emission control device that reduces toxic gases and pollutants in exhaust gas from an internal combustion engine into less-toxic pollutants by catalyzing a redox reaction (an oxidation and a reduction reaction). Catalytic converters are usually used with internal combustion engines fueled by either gasoline or diesel including lean burn engines as well as kerosene heaters and stoves. There are two types of catalytic converters, two-way converters and three-way converters. Two-way converters combine oxygen with carbon monoxide (CO) and unburned hydrocarbons (HC) to produce carbon dioxide (CO₂) and water (H₂O). In 1981, two-way catalytic converters were rendered obsolete by three-way converters which also reduce oxides of nitrogen (NO). However, two-way converters are still used for lean burn engines. This is because three-way converters require either rich or stoichiometric combustion to successfully reduce (NO).

Although catalytic converters are most commonly applied to exhaust systems in automobile, they are also used on electrical generators, forklifts, mining equipment, trucks, buses, locomotives, and motorcycles. They are also used on some wood stoves to control emissions. This is usually in response to government regulation, either through direct environmental regulation or through health and safety regulations. Catalytic converters require a temperature of 800°F (426°C) to effectively convert harmful exhaust gases into inert gases, such as carbon dioxide and water vapour. Therefore, the first catalytic converters were placed close to the engine to ensure fast heating. However, such placement can cause several problems. One of these is vapor lock. As an alternative, catalytic converters were moved to a third of the way back from the engine, and were then placed underneath the vehicle. Two-way catalytic converter was a 2-way oxidation, sometimes called oxi-cat. Thus means two simultaneous tasks:

1. Oxidation of carbon monoxide: $2\text{CO} + \text{O}_2 = 2\text{CO}_2$.
2. Oxidation of hydrocarbons (unburnt and partially burned fuel) to carbon dioxide and water: $\text{C}_x\text{H}_{2x+2} + (\frac{3x+1}{2})\text{O}_2 = x\text{CO}_2 + (x+1)\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - a combustion reaction.

This type of catalytic converter is widely used on diesel engines to reduce hydrocarbon and carbon monoxide emission. Three-way catalytic converters (TWC) have the additional advantage of controlling the emission of nitric oxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) both together abbreviated with NO_x and not to be confused with nitrogen oxide (N₂O), which are precursors to acid rain and smog, since 1981, three-way (oxidation-reaction) catalytic converter have been used in vehicle emission control systems in the United States and Canada. A three-way catalytic converter was three simultaneous tasks:

1. $2\text{CO} + 2\text{NO} = 2\text{CO}_2 + \text{N}_2$
2. Hydrocarbon + NO = CO₂ + H₂O + N₂
3. $2\text{H}_2 + 2\text{NO} = 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{N}_2$

Oxidation of carbon monoxide to carbon dioxide: $2\text{CO} + \text{O}_2 = 2\text{CO}_2$

Oxidation of unburnt hydrocarbons HC to carbon dioxide and water in addition to the above NO reaction.

Hydrocarbon + O₂ = H₂O + CO₂

These three reactions occur most efficiently when the catalytic converter receives exhaust from an engine running slightly above stoichiometric point.

Ways of reducing emissions from motor vehicles

Since most pollution from motor vehicles is due to the burning of fuel, you can reduce pollution from these sources by burning less fuel, burning fuel cleaner and burning cleaner fuel.

1. Burning Less Fuel:

- (a) Next time you purchase a vehicle, buy the most fuel efficient vehicle that meets your average daily needs, larger vehicle or trailer for the occasional large load.
- (b) If you have more than one vehicle, use the most fuel-efficient one possible.
- (c) Use transit vehicle or van-pool as often as you can. Doing so three times a week can reduce your fuel consumption up to 50%
- (d) Use bike or walk to avoid fuel use entirely.
- (e) Telecommute (work from a home-based location via phone or internet) to reduce driving. (f) Minimize driving by working and playing closer to home.
- (g) Plan errands to avoid unnecessary driving. (h) Accelerate gradually-a smooth start uses

2. Burn Fuel Cleaner:

- (a) Keep your vehicle well-tuned and tires inflated properly to reduce emissions. (b) Combine errands into one trip-vehicles pollute less when they are warmed up. (c) Avoid idling- idling exhaust contains more pollutants than running exhaust.
- (d) If you purchase a new vehicle, look for a low emission vehicle (LEV).

3. Burn Cleaner Fuel:

- (a) Low-sulfur gasoline reduces pollutants by 10-15%
- (b) 85% ethanol fuel (E85) can be used in flexible fuel vehicles.
- (c) Other alternative transportation fuels such as natural gas a bio-diesel are most practical for fleets of vehicles.

Fortunately, it is not difficult for individuals to reduce the carbon emissions from their vehicles. First, existing vehicle owners who are not planning on buying a new car any time soon should focus on their driving behaviour. Driving only when absolutely necessary and combining many errands into one trip will reduce driving time, and less time spent on the road means reduced carbon emissions. Families and individuals who own more than one automobile can also consider getting rid of extra ones. This usually reduces the amount of time the owner spends on the road. Secondly, all vehicle owners should keep their vehicles properly maintained. Have the exhaust system on a vehicle checked for leaks. And install a pollution control system if there is not one in place or that the

existing one needs replacing. Such steps will reduce the amount of chemicals released into the atmosphere. Finally, vehicle owners should make sure to drive as efficiently as possible. Increased weight leads to more fuel use, so vehicle owners should not carry unnecessary weight in the trunk or passenger sections of their vehicles. Consider switching to a vehicle that gets more miles to the gallon and thereby uses less fuel and produces less emissions. These easy steps will go a long way to helping solve the problem of excessive carbon emission from motor vehicles.

Conclusion and Suggestions

From all indications, emission from motor vehicle exhaust contribute much in the global warming or global warming of our environment. It is very pertinent that the curriculum of automobile technology should be reformed from time to time so as to create enough awareness among scholars and the generally public the implications of motor vehicle emissions. This problem should be identified through the changes in school curriculum so that full knowledge of these emissions should be understood and subsequently solutions or remedies be disclosed.

References

- Azubuiké, C. A. (2018). *Commerce for senior senior secondary schools*: Onitsha: Africana-First Publishers Limited.
- Elom, E. N. (2012). *Influence of basic technology in attaining the objectives of pre-vocational education programme*. Unpublished Doctoral Thesis. Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki.
- Eneh, O. C. (2011). Managing Nigeria's environment: The unresolved issues. *J. Environs Sci. Technol*, 4, 250-263.
- Fafunwa, A. B. (1997). *History of education in Nigeria*. Ibadan: NPS Educational Publishers.
- Ijiga, P. A. (2010). Reforming the Nigerian school curriculum for entrepreneurship and national development. *International Journal of Education Studies* 1(1), 125.
- Kallman, M. (2008). *Air Pollutions Causes, Consequences and Solutions*. Retrieved from <http://earthrends.wri.org/updates/node/325>.
- Kerstetter, J. (2004). *Washington state's greenhouse gas emissions: sources and trends*.
- Lorenz, E.S. (2007). *Potential health effects of pesticides*. Pennsylvania; Pennsylvania State University.
- Okuta, S. & Enoch, B. E. (2018). Academic achievement of motor vehicle mechanic works students taught with constructivist instructional approach in technical colleges in Gombe State, Nigeria. *Vunoklang Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology* Vol 6. PP 60-67, 2018
- Sanusi, A. A. (2003). *Vocational education for self-reliance*. A paper presented at the 5th National Conference of School of Vocational Studies, Abeokuta, Nigeria.
- Uneke, O. (2015). The impact of transportation in agricultural production in a developing country: A case of kolanut production in Nigeria: *International Journal of Agricultural Economics and Rural Development*, 2(2), 47-57.